

**METHODS OF FORMATION OF IMAGINATION, THINKING AND
CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL
INSTITUTIONS**

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Annotation: The following article describes ways to develop imagination, thinking and creative thinking skills in preschoolers. It provides information on the effective use of didactic games.

Keywords: Pupil, creative thinking, preschool organization, didactic games, capital, method, strategy, factor, imagination, thinking, creative ability

INTRODUCTION

In the age of globalization, the task of educating a new generation with a healthy, up-to-date knowledge of the technological process, adapting to problem situations and being able to get out of this situation with rational ideas and views is being put forward. This is a period of high-priority tasks in the development of human capital. Because the conditions created for human capital will bring up a young generation that will realize our dreams for the future. This is also stated in the Strategy of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2021, including the improvement of the education system and the development of human capital as a factor in the rapid development of our country.

It is well known that human capital is valued as a unique asset. It is equal to the value of a person's services, abilities, talents, and qualities during his or her working life. This means that a person is equal to the value of a range of services rendered to himself and his country, using the knowledge and skills acquired in childhood and

adolescence. J. Kendrick, who studied how the United States became a rich country, says that "... the main factor is the focus on human capital".

Today, our state is also working to radically reform the system of continuing education. In particular, a number of regulatory frameworks have been created to further improve the functioning of preschool education institutions. These principles guarantee all the rights of the child. In particular, every child has the right to pre-school education and upbringing. The state guarantees the right of every child to undergo one year of compulsory one-year preparation for general secondary education in state preschool institutions one year before enrollment in general secondary education. The state guarantees the child's pre-school education and upbringing through the provision of pre-school education and upbringing services on the basis of state pre-school education institutions, as well as the organization of alternative forms of education and upbringing.

Well-known scientist G. Schopenhauer said, "Every child is a partial genius, and every genius is a partial child." Such geniuses are nurtured in pre-school education, which is the primary and most important part of continuing education. President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his speech at the solemn event dedicated to the 26 th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan said: Ibn Sina and Ulugbek grow up. I believe in it". In fact, this stage of continuing education is the first step in shaping a creative, socially active and spiritually mature person. Therefore, we need to pay more attention to the formation of creative thinking skills in children during this period.

Today, experts estimate that 70 percent of all information and information a person receives in his or her lifetime is received by the age of five. This means that we need to encourage children to think creatively from pre-school age so that they can grow up to be healthy, educated and mature professionals.

So, we need to organize more play activities with children. Play is a process of moving and understanding object-oriented and social reality. This is a bright and engaging process for the child. Because every child controls his behavior through play, based on free and emotional needs. Most importantly, children are actively

involved in this process. The game allows the child to know a certain thing or object. At the same time, his will, needs and interests, as well as his influence on the process are formed. It is important for the educator to study and analyze the interests and needs of each child and to develop ways to think creatively and pro.

It is clear that educators need to focus more on the needs and interests of children in the organization of play activities. Creative games should be these children's independent, creative, self-made games. Then the scope of creative thinking in children expands and becomes richer. It requires the educator to guide and direct them.

We know that creative play mainly reflects children's impressions, perceptions of and attitudes to existence. In this sense, creative games can be divided into creating or making something, role-playing games, and games played with natural materials. The uniqueness of creative games is that children can not only create or create something, but also play certain roles or find their place in imaginary situations. The distribution of roles or imaginary situations in creative games stimulates the child's thinking and creative thinking skills. Only we, the educators, have to organize these games taking into account the age of the children. Creative games provide children with new knowledge and insights. In this process, they develop in all directions, the process of cognition, sensory culture, speech activity, mental abilities are improved. "Childhood is a period of many questions, opportunities and consequences", -said A. Alder. That's why we shouldn't leave any children's questions unanswered, we should support their every interest. We also need to analyze what games they are interested in and the consequences.

It should be noted that Japanese teachers have found wealth in Uzbekistan. They found a way to save the young Japanese generation in Uzbekistan. Some of our people are collecting and taking action games that they don't play "modern" and teaching them to their super-modern children. The reason is that modern children's games have become too technocratic. They lack human spirit, charm, pleasure and emotion. This means that we need to make effective use of didactic games based on modern pedagogical technologies, as well as national games inherited from our

ancestors. Because these games have their own characteristics, through which positive qualities in children, such as intimacy, cohesiveness, willpower, are formed through certain actions. Of course, this requires taking into account the age characteristics of the child.

In preschool, the toys they play also play an important role in developing children's creative thinking skills through games. In this regard, our first president enthusiastically said:

- "... given the fact that every child first understands the world through the objects around him, including toys, their role in human education. it becomes clear that it is incomparable. The image of the toy is imprinted on the child's imagination like a stone carving and stays in his mind for a lifetime. As a child grows up, he chooses a career, what path he will take in the future, how he will base his life on moral and spiritual principles, and, of course, what toys he grew up with as a child. will be determined. ” This idea proves once again that we should pay attention to the choice of toys that are produced today.

CONCLUSION

This means that the organization of play activities is very important in the formation of creative thinking skills in preschoolers. The reason is that play is the most important technology that determines the level of children's future learning and work activities, their attitude to people and the environment. On the basis of play activities, the child's cognitive activity develops, he learns to think creatively, independently, his abilities are formed, and, of course, to read and learn on the basis of the conditions created in the system of continuous education.

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